

THE ESSENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF MOTHER TONGUE EDUCATION

Ahmadova Ferangiz Hamza qizi
BukhSU III stage student

Annotation: In this article, the essence of pedagogical technologies in the process of mother tongue education is scientifically and theoretically based.

Key words: Figurative thinking, young age, children's thinking, basic form, quality, recognition, school textbooks, training manuals, didactic, handouts, etc.

Introduction: Today, a number of scientific views and pedagogical theories have been formed that serve to organize the primary education process, increase its effectiveness, and improve the pedagogical and psychological foundations of educating children of primary school age, which are unitary in nature (provides an opportunity to organize an educational process that serves to ensure the maturity of the individual, its complete formation and development, unlike the traditional (subject) type of education.

Primary education is considered an important link in the general secondary education system, it forms the desire and skills of the child to study and learn, involves the child in highly formed cognitive activities, manifests in the child's psyche. aims to stabilize existing justice and goodness.

Review of the literature: The content of education in primary grades is determined not by subjects, but by fields of study. given in the standards, in which he finds the continuity between the process of preschool education and the process of primary education, interdisciplinarity, humanism, and nationalism of education. lim is given.

Figurative thinking is recognized as the main form of thinking of young children and is taken into account in the preparation of school textbooks, training manuals, didactic and distribution materials. The development of figurative and logical thinking is closely related to the development of children's speech.

This feature of primary education is taken into account when determining the content and amount of mathematics and mother tongue education. In primary education, knowledge is given in the form of definition, understanding, and information, and it also serves to clarify, systematize, and develop knowledge acquired in the form of imagination during preschool education.

The expected effective result of primary education is the principles of primary education and its organization, textbooks, instructional manuals, methods created on

the basis of the ideas recognized in the constitution of primary education. recommendations, methods and methods of organizing primary education, innovative ideas, new generation means of teaching.

However, in our opinion, it is appropriate to note the role of the primary school teacher in this process. A primary school teacher has different aspects in terms of essence and characteristics than a high school teacher.

If the teacher of the upper class focuses more on the deep and systematic teaching of the rules, edges and features of the specialty, the differential aspects of education, the teacher of the primary class focuses on the complex of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, methods of increasing the effectiveness of education. , armed with factors and tools, having a perfect knowledge of the scientific and theoretical bases of mathematics, mother tongue, nature, human and society education fields, based on the age characteristics of the child, the way to teach the general aspects of science, that is, to provide integrative education grows.

In order to direct the child from playing activities to educational activities, the teacher should help the child to manage his own activities, to feel responsibility, to plan time, to be attentive, to look forward to a promising future by appreciating goodness. is also a responsible educator. Another no less important aspect of a primary school teacher is the integration of primary and general education subjects and the interaction of the subjects of primary education. is to organize based on the principles of relativity. The teacher's knowledge of foreign languages, the ability to use new generation teaching tools, advanced work practices, pedagogical technologies in the educational process, having a comprehensive worldview and being able to influence the child, Incorporation of intellectual qualities is also one of the important aspects.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to take into account these specific features of the primary education process in the training of future primary school teachers.

The future elementary school teachers will be armed with the factors, tools and methods of forming imaginative and logical thinking in the school by following the scientific-theoretical, methodological foundations of preschool and primary education, the principles of connection, coherence. We believe that teaching extracurricular activities and their organization courses in the mother tongue to elementary school teachers will also have a positive effect.

Today, the rapid growth of society, the development of science and technology, and the positive results of the ongoing reforms have an impact on educational processes, as well as on all other fields.

The role and importance of lessons on the formation of students' speech is great in expanding the range of thought of a junior high school student, in acquiring the basic literacy of the art of communication, in the implementation of a complex educational process.

These requirements include regularly increasing the level of students' thinking, ensuring full speech and spelling literacy of students.

There are many options of methods and exercises used in the methodology of teaching the mother tongue to improve students' literacy, to form grammatical concepts, and to improve their speech and spelling literacy. Educational games play an important role in the strengthening of phonetic, grammatical, orthographic concepts, perfect formation of speaking skills, among the exercises specified in the methodology. , fatigue is eliminated, on the other hand, children's thinking process accelerates, and the detailed formation of certain defined skills becomes easier.

Conclusion: It is known that the younger the student, the more interesting game elements used in the lessons should be. on the other hand, on the other hand, it eliminates aspects such as inhumanity, silence, and shyness in some children. So, the game process makes drastic changes in the psychology of the student. during the course, the student begins to understand the essence of abstract grammatical and orthographic concepts, signs common to many words begin to take place in his memory, he begins to understand the essence of orthographic - orthographic concepts in oral and written speech, orthoepic in written speech - orthographic defects are reduced. Educational games ensure the free behavior of the class team, the effectiveness of the lesson increases. The active participation of the majority of students in the game is ensured, and there is an opportunity to put rating points.

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